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SOME TOXICOLOGICAL STUDIES OF ONE SIDHA FORMULATION “KODASURI VEERAVAIPPU”

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ABSTRACT

The efficacy parameters of present day medicine depends on various scientific verifications such as pharmacological, pharmacokinetic, teratological and toxicological parameters. Ayurvedic and Sidhha medical practices, although age old methods of medicinal practice, have to prove their efficacy in these lines to get wider attention, recognition and acceptability. The present report is to study the toxicological effects of one Sidhha medicine, Kodasuri veeravaippu, on animal model. This medicine is used to treat inflammatory conditions such as rheumatism and arthritis in Sidhha practice. The parameters studied were water consumption, food consumption, body weight, kidney function test, liver function test and hematological parameters. The duration of the Study was for 45 days. Two dose levels of the test drug 'Kodasuri veeravaippu' were used (9.75 mg/kg and 16.15 mg/kg). Each group consists of six animals (three animals /sex /group). The drug was administered orally once daily for 45 days. It was observed that the medicine was quite safe when used at a lower dose of 6.75mg/kg, whereas, there was some moderate side effects, well within the permissible limit, at 16.15 mg /kg. Further work is on to understand the medicinal efficacy of this drug.

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda and Sidhha are age old medical practices of India and majority of Indians follow some or the other form of these medicinal practices. Although made up of natural materials like plants, animals or some salts, there is always a question mark about the toxicity of medicines. Even heavy metals like mercury, lead, gold and silver are used in the preparation of these medicines; there is all the more concern about the short and long term toxicity effects of such medicines. It is claimed by the scriptures that during the processing of these medicines the toxic levels of these metals are reduced to permissible limits and they are safe.

The present day scientific demand is to prove the veracity of such claims. The Ayurvedic and Sidhha medicines are prepared by the age old protocols and there are no experimental verifications at toxicological, pharmacological and pharmacokinetic levels about the safety and efficacy. This is one of the major reasons for these medical practices being criticized and due recognition is not given.

The present study is one step in this direction. The presence of heavy metal in Kodasuri veeravaippu like Mercury is reported to be well within the permissible limits. [1, 2] There are some reports on scientific efficacy of Kodasuri veeravaippu and some other Ayurvedic and Sidhha preparations. [3-14]. The present study deals with the toxicological analysis of Kodasuri veeravaippu on animal model

MATERIALS AND METHODS

EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS

Adult albino Wistar rats of either sex weighing around 125-150gms were used. The animals were maintained at normal room temperature with a humidity of 55 + 5⁰c. All the animals were fed with pellet diet obtained from Poultry Research Station, Nandanam, Chennai – 35 and tap water *ad libitum* throughout the experimental period. The animals were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions before experimental procedures were started. The experimental protocol for the drug 'Kodasuri veeravaippu' (AJ/IAEC/10/11) was approved by the CPCSEA/IAEC of Mohamed Sathak A. J College of Pharmacy, Sholinganallur, Chennai.

ACUTE ORAL TOXICITY STUDY (LD₅₀ Determination)

For carrying out oral toxicity study OECD guidelines 423 was followed. It is a stepwise procedure with three animals of a single sex per step. Depending on the mortality and/or morbidity of the animals a few steps may be necessary to judge the toxicity of the test substance. This procedure has advantage over other methods because of minimal usage of animals while allowing for acceptable data. The method uses defined doses (5, 50, 300, 2000mg/kg body weight) and the results allow a substance to be ranked and classified according to the globally harmonized system. The starting dose of the drug 'Kodasuri veeravaippu' was 2000 mg/kg bodyweight p.o. The dose was administered to the rats which were fasted overnight with water *ad libitum* and observed for signs of toxicity. All animals were died at dose of 2000 mg/kg. Then 300 mg/kg dose level was administrated to the rats which were fasted overnight with water *ad libitum* and observed for signs of toxicity. Two animals were died. Then 50 mg/kg dose was administrated for another three animals which were fasted overnight with water *ad libitum* and observed for signs of toxicity, this time no mortality was registered. Thus L.D₅₀ of the test drug ranges from 50 mg/kg to 300 mg/kg. At the dose of 130 mg / kg was administered for the six animals as per the sidhha literature reference of per day human dose of the test drug. Exactly three animals were died. Therefore, the L.D₅₀ of the drug 'Kodasuri veeravaippu' was determined as 130 mg/ kg of rat. The effective dose of the drug is 13 mg/kg. The effective dose was once again tried with another three rats and were observed for 72 hours and found normal for symptoms like change in skin color, salivation, diarrhea, sleep, tremors, convulsions and also respiratory, autonomic and CNS effects.

SUBACUTE TOXICITY STUDY

PROCEDURE

The duration of the Study was 45 days. Two dose levels of the test drug 'Kodasuri veeravaippu' were used (9.75 mg/kg and 16.15 mg/kg). Each group consists of six animals (Three animals /sex /group). The drug was administered orally once daily for 45days. On 46th day the animal was anaesthetized and blood was collected by retro orbital puncture. Hematological parameters were evaluated. Serum was separated and biochemical parameters were estimated.

Hematological studies

The following hematological parameters were estimated by standard procedures.

- A. Total R.B.C. count (Ghai, 1993) [15]
- B. Total W.B.C. Count (Ghai, 1993). [15]
- C. Haemoglobin (Hb) concentration (Ghai., 1993). [15]
- D. Assay of Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST) (Ghai, 1993), Engelhardi and Norges, 1970). [15, 16]
- E. Assay of Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) (Bergmeyer, 1972). [17]
- F. Assay of Total Bilirubin (TB) (Jendrassik and Grof, 1938; Schellong and Wende, 1960). [18, 19]
- G. Blood urea (Kassirer, 1971). [20]
- H. Serum creatinine (Ullmann and Bonitz, 1976). [21]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of Toxicological studies are shown in Table 1 to Table 6 indicating various parameters.

Table 1 .Indicate the effect of Kodasuri veeravaippu on water consumption of animals.

Groups	Average water consumption for 24 hr per animal (ml)		
	1 day	14 th day	28 th day
I- control	14.5	16.1	15.9
II- low dose (6.75 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	13.3	15.2	14.9
III- high dose of (16.15 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	17.3	16.4	13.8

Table 2. Indicates the effect of Food Consumption rate on animals.

Groups	Average feed consumption for 24 hr per animal (grams)		
	1 st day	14 th day	28 th day
I- control	10.3	11.5	13.2
II- low dose (6.75 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	10.3	10.8	12.9
III- high dose of (16.15 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	09.5	09.9	12.3

BODY WEIGHT

Table 3. Indicates the effect of Kodasuri veeravaippu on body weigh parameters.

Groups	Body weight in grams / animal		
	1 st day	14 th day	28 th day
I- control	135.2	142.3	151.7
II- low dose (6.75 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	134.2	140.5	151.2
III- high dose of (16.15 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	135.3	147.9	151.2

Table 4. KIDNEY FUNCTION TEST.

Groups	Kidney function tests (mg/dl)		
	Urea	Uric acid	Creatinine
I- control	25	3.8	0.3
II- low dose(6.75 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	26	4	0.4
III- high dose of (16.15 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	27	4.2	0.4

Table 5. LIVER FUNCTION TESTS.

Groups	Liver function tests (IU/L)			Total Bilirubin (mg/dl)
	AST	ALT	Alkaline phosphatase	
I- control	81	33	23	0.6
II- low dose (6.75 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	84	34	25	0.7
III- high dose of (16.15 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	86	39	26	0.7

Table 6. HEAMATOLOGY.

Groups	RBC count (million cells/c.mm)	WBC count (cells/c.mm)	Hb(%)
I- control	4	6900	12.2
II- low dose (6.75 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	3.4	6100	12.4
III- high dose of (16.15 mg/kg) Kodasuri veeravaippu	3.9	6400	12.8

The above results are discussed in the following paragraphs.

WATER CONSUMPTION

Table 1 indicates that, while comparing with control group animals, not much change is observed in the water consumption in test group animals indicating that there is no significant effect of test medicine on water consumption parameter.

FOOD CONSUMPTION

Table 2 indicates that there is no appreciable increase or decrease in the food consumption due to the drug. This proves that there is no stress involved in terms of food consumption.

BODY WEIGHT

Table 3 indicated no significant variation in weight was noticed in low dose group. Weight gain is noticed in high dose group of 'Kodasuri veeravaippu', on 14th day of observation, which shows the positive aspect of the test drug.

KIDNEY FUNCTION TEST

Table 4 indicated that there was a slight increase in the levels of blood urea, uric acid and creatinine in higher dose treated animals when compared to control but they were well within the range. These results indicate that Kodasuri veeravaippu does not have any adverse effect on the function of kidneys.

LIVER FUNCTION TEST

Table 5 indicates that in high dose group of test drug SGOT, SGPT, Alkaline phosphatase is raised within the normal range than the low dose group animals. This shows the low dose level is better than the high dose of the test drug.

HAEMETOLOGY

Table 6 indicated that both test drug groups show reduction in R.B.C count and W.B.C count. Mild increase in HB level is noticed in the both test groups.

All the above parameters studied indicated that at lower dose of 6.75 mg/kg dose Kodasuri veeravaippu works well without any appreciable side effects and this dose level must be correspondingly adjusted when it is used for patients.

CONCLUSIONS

From the above results and discussion it is clear that Kodasuri veeravaippu is toxicologically well within the optimum level and its consumption for the cure of inflammatory diseases is acceptable. Further work in this direction to validate this medicine is under progress.

Abbreviations

R.B. C : Red Blood Cells

W. B. C : White Blood Cells

Hb. : Hemoglobin

ALT : Alanine Amino Transferase

AST : Aspartate Amino Transferase

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Conflict of Interest Statement:

The authors affirm that no conflict of interest exists among them.

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